

04 On Discrete Euclidean Space

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22 December 2020

The paper is the fourth post of the blog “Discrete Euclidean Space” at <https://www.conceptualframeworks.org>. The post is about the meaning of non-locality in relation to the basic properties of the structure of discrete space.

Non-locality

The synchronized topological deformation of all the units of the structure of discrete space at exactly the same moment – because of the tessellation of the volume of the universe – shows a type of instantaneous action we have termed “non-locality” in theoretical physics. But the mutual influence of the individual units of discrete space by the mechanism of topological deformation cannot explain a type of non-locality that is known in theoretical physics as “entanglement”.^[1]

It is clear, the mechanism of topological deformation cannot elucidate why 2 entangled photons can influence each other at exactly the same moment but at a distance that eliminates a mutual interference with the speed of light. Besides that, the influence of the topological deformation – 1 quantum – over a distance of e.g. 1 km is totally negligible. So there are *hidden variables*.

The problem isn’t restricted to the entanglement of 2 photons, the mutual influence of everything we can observe in the universe is incomprehensible if the structure of discrete space is the foundation of observable reality. The problem is visualised in figure 1. It shows the schematic grid of the minimal length scale and the light of a bulb.

figure 1

Suppose that the cube is the basic geometrical shape of the units of discrete space. The transfer of quanta is the topological deformation of the faces of the unit so I have to observe 6 dominant directions of emitted electromagnetic waves. But that’s not what I observe. The light of the bulb is homogeneous distributed over the volume around the bulb. I can imagine some possible explanations but even an astronomer who is observing the light of a distant star will not notice a distribution in preferred directions at a distance of many light years.

In other words, the direction of emitted light waves don’t show the existence of the structure of the units of discrete space. The speed of light is the only velocity of light waves thus the homogeneous distribution of the light in vacuum space far away from the source of the light is like magic.

figure 2

Instantaneous influence

The image above (2) shows the same schematic unit that is displayed in post 3, figure 2. But a part of the invariant volume of the unit is drawn as an inscribed sphere, actually a scalar. In theoretical physics the whole volume of the universe is pervaded by a scalar field, the Higgs field. But this is not the primary reason to propose that every unit of discrete space “envelopes” a scalar of the Higgs field.

In nature the geometrical shape of the sphere is dominant at every scale size. In other words, one of the basic properties of every unit of discrete space must be a spherical shape forming mechanism that is responsible for the spatial properties of every unit of discrete space.

If the inscribed sphere of a unit is the undistorted part of the spherical shape forming mechanism of the volume of a unit, the other part must be the distorted spherical shape forming mechanism of the unit. Simply because all the units of discrete space tessellate the universe.

figure 3

The internal spherical shape forming mechanism of all the units of discrete space will force an internal spherical configuration till a further expansion of the sphere is obstructed by the other units around. The result is figure 3, the compact configuration of the scalars of the Higgs field in vacuum space.^{[1][2]}

The deformable part of every unit is involved in the synchronous and continuous topological deformation of the units of discrete space. These deformations create corresponding vectors inside the scalars of the Higgs field in vacuum space. Vacuum space itself is everywhere in the universe except inside the boundary of nuclei and black holes. The image below (4) shows the internal vectors of 1 scalar.

figure 4

Topological deformations create corresponding vectors and visa versa. But topological deformations are transferred between the elements with the speed of light. Vectors, on the other hand, act instantaneous because vectors don't transfer energy. Vectors only determine the direction of the topological deformations. Actually, the hierarchy of all the vectors within a scalar determine the distribution of the quantum of topological deformation between the faces of a unit within the flat Higgs field (figure 2).

Conclusion: there are hidden variables and these hidden variables are the scalar vectors within the flat Higgs field (vacuum space).

The brief explanation isn't meant to elucidate all the mathematical details in this post. Because the subject is non-locality and the existence of scalar vectors makes it clear why everything in the universe is influencing everything at exactly the same moment. Because the measured entanglement of 2 photons shows that instantaneous influence as a basic property of nature exists everywhere in the universe.

Moreover, the distribution of phenomena like photons in space show that the distinct position in space isn't independent from everything around. Nevertheless, we use this kind of phenomenological reasoning in theoretical physics. We even have a name for it: *common sense*.

References:

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 2. P.W. Higgs (1964), "Broken Symmetries and the Masses of Gauge Bosons". *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 13 (16): 508
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Phenomenological physics

What will remain from Einstein's theory of Special relativity if time is a constant (t_c), the speed of light (c) is the *one and only* universal velocity – in relation to the transfer of energy in space – and nature shows to be non-local?

I suppose that Einstein's theory of Special relativity is still important for the interpretation of observations and experiments with the help of the reference frame of phenomenological physics. But as a theory that can be used to elucidate the mechanism that create reality the theory of Special relativity is obsolete.

Unfortunately phenomenological physics is not limited to the theory of Special relativity, and related, the theory of General relativity. Because the minimal length scale (l_c) is not only responsible for the concept of "asymptotic freedom", the synchronous and constant deformation of all the

units of discrete space is the origin of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle too. And particles that decay within $0,5 \times 10^{-15}$ m cannot be real particles.

The phenomenological point of view – reasoning in the way we interpret sensory reality – isn't capable to unravel the confusing mixture of empiric data. Nevertheless, the grand theories in physics, the Standard model of elementary particles and forces, Einstein's theory of Special and General relativity and the Standard cosmological model are created with the help of the phenomenological point of view.